

BLOOD COUNT ALTERATIONS IN COVID-19 PNEUMONIA**Jardan Mihaela,**

*Student, Faculty of General Medicine,
State University of Medicine and Pharmacy "Nicolae Testemitanu"
Republic of Moldova, Chisinau*

Feghiu Maria

*Associate professor, Department of Internal Medicine – Semiology
State University of Medicine and Pharmacy "Nicolae Testemitanu"
Republic of Moldova, Chisinau*

Abstract

The COVID-19 pandemic represents a global crisis of the 21st century and one of the biggest challenges faced by society after the Second World War. Once it appeared in Asia, the virus spread to all continents. It has not only created crisis in health sector, but also caused devastating damage in the economic, political, social fields. Although more than 3 years have passed since the WHO reported the new virus, the pandemic has not regained its end due to mutagenic character, insufficient vaccination and symptoms with multiorgan damage.

Keywords: virus, COVID-19 pandemic, pneumonia, blood changes,

Introduction

In early December 2019 in the city of Wuhan, the capital of China's Hubei province, several cases of pneumonia of unknown origin were identified. The pathogen of this infection, officially named on 11.02.2020 SARS-Cov-2 „ Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2”, represents an RNA virus, β coronavirus[3,4]. The final diagnosis for COVID-19 pneumonia is made using an X-ray, but blood changes are also important, from the simplest changes (increased inflammatory markers) to leukopenia, trombocytopenia requiring transfer to specialized departments with mechanical ventilation .

Aim of the study

Due to the fact that COVID-19 is a continuing threat to people's lives caused by a delayed approach to

its prevention, diagnosis and treatment, we aimed to identify the first changes in blood tests that occur and can be the trigger pillars of a fatal cascade.

Materials and methods

The study included 80 patients with the diagnosis of COVID-19 Pneumonia, treated in the General Therapy department of the „Sfântul Arhangel Mihail” Clinical Hospital, Republic of Moldova, during the years 2020-2021. The COVID-19 Pneumonia developed more frequently in men 47(59%), compared to women- 33(41%). The database of the selected material was processed statistically using Microsoft Excel.

Results and discussions

Following the analysis of patient observation records, a prevalence was observed among women aged 61-70 years, among men aged 51-70(Figure 1).

Figure 1. Distribution of COVID-19 Pneumonia patients according to age

Analyzing the blood count, we note that the level of leukocytes undergoes various changes during the hospitalization of patients, depending on the severity of the disease. Most patients at admission had the level of leukocytes in the norm, then their decrease in mild forms occurred. Leukopenia in many centers was the primary differentiation indicator of COVID-19 pneumonia and non-COVID pneumonia. In some patients, however, after 4-7 days after admission, the level of

leukocytes was elevated, on account of neutrophils (Figure 2)[6]. These changes were mainly determined in elderly patients with comorbidities and increased risk of mortality, who needed transfer to specialized ICU departments. Those with milder forms of COVID-19, 13 (16%) patients experienced mild leukopenia. Other changes that were predictors of the need for special care were patients with anemia - Hb, low erythrocytes and hematocrit levels, lymphocytopenia and

thrombocytopenia. In 12(15%) of patients, serum ferritin with moderately elevated levels was identified, correlated with lactacidemia of 4 (5%) of them, subsequently developing ARDS and being placed in centers with ATI. At the same time, it was shown that these patients suffer a certain degree of decompensated tissue

hypoxia, which coordinated the doctors to study the clinical signs at the neurological level, to determine the degree of CNS damage correlated with the level of ferritin in the blood. It was determined of those 12 patients with elevated ferritin, headache was recorded in all.

Figure 2. Dynamics of leukocytes changes during hospitalization

Another changed indicator in COVID-19 pneumonia is the level of eosinophils. Comparing the analyzes of patients with bilateral pneumonia and those with unilateral pneumonia, more marked eosinopenia is observed in those with bilateral damage[7]. The level of inflammatory markers is determined increased to ESR, C-reactive protein, procalcitonin. The biochemical markers also underwent changes, the elevation of the hepatic markers: ALAT and ASAT, the level of bilirubin, as well as the renal ones: serum creatinine and urea.

Blood glucose level is also changed. 1/3 of the patients were admitted with the glucose level at the upper limit of the norm, then during hospitalization were observed elevations of blood glucose, another 2/3 of the patients were admitted with increased blood glucose and during the evolution of the pathology collided with risky increases of glucose, which significantly increases the risk of mortality, as well as the use of insulin, more beneficial is the administration of metformin[2,5].

Table 1

Blood glucose dynamics during hospitalization

Number of patients (total=30)	Glycemia on admission (mmol/l)	Glycemia during hospitalization (mmol/l)
8	5-6,5	7-8,5
22	10-11	14-16

The increase in D-dimers is correlated with IL-2R on Day 5, IL-6, and C-reactive protein on day 10. At the same time, the association between the elevation of D-dimers, APTT, ALAT/ ASAT, CRP, fibrinogen, LDH ,

PT, CBC(platelets and lymphocytes in acute phases) and the decrease of albumin, fibrinogen and PT in late phases, may lead to increased risk of venous thromboembolism in COVID-19[1].

Changes identified in laboratory tests

Changes	Number of patients (percentages)
Anaemia	24(30%)
Leukocytosis	24(33%)
Leukopenia	13(16%)
Thrombocytopenia	43(54%)
Lymphocytopenia	32(40%)
Neutrophilia	22(33%)
Eosinopenia	10(13%)
VSH ↑	80(100%)
PCR ↑	78(98%)
Feritin ↑	12(15%)
Lactic acid ↑	4(5%)
Hyperglycaemia	30(38%)
Fibrinogen ↑	34(43%)
D-dimeri ↑	45(56%)
INR ↑	12(15%)
ALAT ↑	6(8%)
ASAT ↑	10(13%)
Bilirub ↑	8(10%)
Cholesterol ↑	16(20%)
Triglycerides ↑	14(18)
Creatinine ↑	4(5%)
Uree ↑	5(6%)
Procalcitonin ↑	17(21%)

Conclusions

Patients with mild forms of the COVID-19 pneumonia have leukopenia, increased inflammatory markers, moderate hyperglycemia, while patients with severe forms have leukocytosis, thrombocytopenia, anemia, changes in coagulogram and blood biochemistry with developing kidney, liver, heart failure, patients who subsequently will require care in ICU departments.

References

1. Eljilany I, Elzouki AN. Vascular Health and Risk Management. 2020 [cited 2023 Feb 21]; <http://doi.org/10.2147/VHRM.S280962>
2. High blood glucose at admission, insulin use raise risk for COVID-19 mortality in diabetes <https://www.healio.com/news/endocrinology/20210429/high-blood-glucose-at-admission-insulin-use-raise-risk-for-covid19-mortality-in-diabetes>
3. MINISTERUL SĂNĂTĂȚII AL REPUBLICII MOLDOVA INFECT, IA CU CORONAVIRUS DE TIP NOU (COVID-19) Protocol clinic național (ediția VI).

4. Oldani S, Ravaglia C, Bensai S, Bertolovic L, Ghirotti C, Puglisi S, et al. Pathophysiology of light phenotype SARS-CoV-2 interstitial pneumonia: from histopathological features to clinical presentations. *Pulmonology*. 2022 Sep 1;28(5):333–44.

5. Schlesinger S, Neuenschwander M, Lang A, Pafili K, Kuss O, Herder C, et al. Risk phenotypes of diabetes and association with COVID-19 severity and death: a living systematic review and meta-analysis. *Diabetologia*, <https://www.healio.com/news/endocrinology/20210429/high-blood-glucose-at-admission-insulin-use-raise-risk-for-covid19-mortality-in-diabetes>

6. Urbano M, Costa E, Galdes C. Hematological changes in SARS-COV-2 positive patients. *Hematol Transfus Cell Ther*. 2022 Apr 1;44(2):218–24.

7. Yan B, Yang J, Xie Y, Tang X. Relationship between blood eosinophil levels and COVID-19 mortality. *World Allergy Organization Journal*. 2021 Mar 1;14(3):100521.